

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)

**Deliverable 3.3, SOPs for all Physicochemical Methods,
Annex I.**

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PARTICLE SIZE CHARACTERIZATION IN COLLOIDAL SILICA EXP320 USING DYNAMIC LIGHT SCATTERING			

1 SUMMARY

The method can be used to determine the hydrodynamic diameter (Z-average size) of particles in colloidal silica, using dynamic light scattering (DLS). The method has been validated for the product Levasil EXP320, and accurate results can therefore only be ensured for this product.

2 GENERAL INFORMATION

The DLS instrument is situated in the instrument room in the ground floor lab of the TK building. A copy of this instruction can be found in a folder next to the instrument. DLS is only suitable for samples with monodisperse and very narrow particle size distributions. For more polydisperse samples, the value of the Z-average size is larger than the real average particle size.

3 HAZARDS AND SAFETY

There are no hazards with this method in addition to the general risks of laboratory work. General laboratory clothing and protection (safety goggles, gloves and protective shoes) must be worn. See risk assessment report 18-21

4 QUALITY ASSURANCE OF ANALYTICAL METHOD

The control sample "QP DLS sol" (EXP320) should be measured at every occasion of analysis. The method has been validated for Levasil EXP320 only.

5 APPARATUS

- 5.1 DLS-instrument, Malvern Zetasizer
- 5.2 Disposable polystyrol/polystyren cuvettes of type DTS0012.
- 5.3 Automatic pipettes 100-1000 µl, with associated pipette tips
- 5.4 Plastic vial, 12 ml volume
- 5.5 Plastic syringe, 20 ml volume
- 5.6 Syringe filters, 0,1 µm cut-off

6 CHEMICALS

- 6.1 Sodium chloride solution 1,00 mol/l
- 6.2 Sodium chloride (for the preparation of new sodium chloride solution)
- 6.3 Ultrapure water

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7 PROCEEDURE

7.1 Start of the instrument
Start the DLS instrument using the on/off button at the back of the instrument. Allow the instrument to warm up for 30 min. Open the software *Zetasizer Software* on the computer. Create a data file via *File / New / Measurement file*. Name the file with date and your personal initials under: *C:\Users\bhssol.D30\Documents\Malvern Instruments\Zetasizer\Measurement Data\CA\EXP320\[current month]*

7.2 Sample preparation

7.2.1 Preparation of 20 mmol/l NaCl-solution (durable for one week):
Using an automatic pipette, transfer 4 ml of 1,00 mol/l NaCl-solution to a 200 ml volumetric flask. Adjust the volume to 200 ml with ultrapure water.

7.2.2 Dilution of sample

The sample of colloidal silica is diluted with filtered 20 mmol/l NaCl-solution to a final volume of 10 ml. Fill a 20 ml plastic syringe with 20 mmol/l NaCl-solution, place a syringe filter (0,1 µm cut-off) on the syringe and filter 5 ml of the solution into a 12 ml plastic vial. Add an appropriate volume of colloidal silica (V_{sol}) to the vial according to:

$$V_{sol} = \frac{10 \times C_{smp}}{C_{sol}} \quad (1)$$

where C_{sol} is the SiO₂-concentration of the colloidal silica and C_{smp} is the desired SiO₂-concentration after dilution to 10 ml. Filter additional NaCl-solution to the vial, to a final volume of 10 ml. Seal the vial and mix.

C_{smp} should be adjusted so that the *attenuator* (inversely dependent on the signal-intensity) of the DLS measurement is in the range 6-8. The required C_{smp} depend on the particle size, and is typically between 0,1 % (for 100 nm particles) and 1 % SiO₂ (for 15 nm particles). For EXP320 (particle diameter around 30 nm and $C_{sol} = 40$ %,) a suitable value of C_{prov} is 0,5 %, and V_{sol} is therefore 0,125 ml.

7.3 Analysis

Make two replicates for each sample, i.e. analyze the diluted sample twice, in separate cuvettes.

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Ensure that the disposable cuvette is free from scratches. Avoid touching the lower half of the cuvette. Rinse the inside of the cuvette with 20 mmol/l NaCl-lösning, and fill it with 2 ml of sample. Ensure that there are not bubbles in the cuvette. Insert the cuvette in the instrument with the arrow on the cuvette towards you, and close the hatch of the instrument.

In the scrolling list (see picture below), chose "Browse for SOP". Click the green arrow to the right of the list and chose SOP "SI087" under: *C:\Users\bhssol.D30\Documents\Malvern Instruments\Zetasizer\SOP\Size\CA*

Fill in the sample number (from LIMS) in the dialog box, and click "OK". A new window is opened in which "start" is clicked to start the analysis. Log files and data is now shown in a number of tabs. When the analysis is done, close the window to return to the measurement file where the results are shown.

Fill a new cuvette with the same sample and repeat the measurements for the second replicate. Thereafter the control sample is analyzed, also with two replicates.

8 CALCULATING AND REPORTING

8.1 Calculation of mean values

The method measures each replicate five times, and returns five values for each parameter. In the result table, these are named by the sample number + a number 1-5.

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Select the five measurements for the first replicate. Right click the selected rows and chose "Create average result". A new row is now created, showing the mean value of the five measurements for each parameter. Repeat the procedure for the five measurements of the second replicate.

8.2 Controlling the quality of the measurements

Check that the value of the attenuator (inversely dependent on the signal) is in the range 6-8. If the attenuator is out of this range, dilute the sample to a higher concentration (if the attenuator is too low) or a lower concentration (if the attenuator is too high) and re-analyze the sample.

Check that the value of "Pdl" (polydispersity index) is $<0,1$ and that the value of "Pk 1 Area Int" (indicating the monodispersity) is $>95\%$. If these requirements are not fulfilled, prepare a new sample (mix the colloidal silica before) and re-analyze. If the Pdl and Pk 1 Area Int are still out of the required ranges, the sample may be damaged (i.e., aggregated) or the product may be too polydisperse to be analyzed by DLS.

8.3 Reporting

Print out the result list (bhsprinter 109), attach it to the primary data sheet and store in the primary data folder.

Manually enter the mean values for Z-ave size and Pdl for the two replicates under *Value 1* value *Value 2* in LIMS.
Report the control sample in the same way.

9 WASTE DISPOSAL

The diluted samples can be poured out in the sink. The concentrated colloidal silica is returned to the customer.

10 ADDITIONAL INSTRUCTIONS

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REFERENCES

1. Risk assessment: "Mätning av partikelstorlek med DLS 18-21 "
2. Validation report: "Validering av Dynamisk Ljusspridning (DLS) för storlekskaraktärisering av SiO₂-nanopartiklar i kiselsyrasol EXP320"